

LEVELS OF ASSESSMENT OF TRAINING RESULTS IN THE EDUCATIONAL SYSTEM**Khudiyeva F.***PhD in Pedagogy, Associate Professor
Azerbaijan State Pedagogical University, Azerbaijan***Abstract**

Currently, as in many areas, radical reforms are being implemented in the field of education in the Republic of Azerbaijan. The main goal of these reforms is to improve the quality of education and ensure its development, taking into account the needs and requirements of society. In this regard, it has become necessary to review the factors determining the quality of education, primarily the content of education, teacher training and assessment systems. The development of a new assessment system has been identified as one of the priority areas in the Education Sector Development Project. The creation of modern assessment mechanisms for improving the training and teaching process, obtaining objective data on the achievements of students across the country, as well as monitoring state education standards is an important task. Since the main indicator in determining the quality of education is the student's learning results, the objective assessment of these results is considered the most reliable source that reveals quality.

Keywords: quality, education, students, monitoring, development.

The Assessment Concept in the general education system of the Republic of Azerbaijan (hereinafter referred to as the Concept) is designed to manage measures related to assessment issues in education in the country in the coming years. The main content of the document is aimed at determining the principles that ensure the legitimacy of assessment activities, determining the leading directions of this activity, strengthening the social status of institutions implementing assessment measures, and using assessment to meet the needs of training and education. This document, as a framework document, has been prepared in accordance with the requirements of the Law on Education of the Republic of Azerbaijan, the Education Reform Program of the Republic of Azerbaijan and the state education policy, modern world standards of assessment, and plays the role of a basis for the principles of the new assessment system. The document interprets the main principles and areas of activity of intra-school, national and international assessment. The concept also envisages the preparation of additional documents in the form of precise rules and regulations to ensure the reliability and effectiveness of each type of assessment.

The concept is directly related to the national curriculum framework document developed for the purpose of modernization and renewal of general education in Azerbaijan and is an integral part of it. The creation of assessment mechanisms and tools is considered the next stage after the development of content standards and subject curricula of education.

The new assessment system ensures the following:

1. fulfilling the role of an important tool for making positive changes in education; providing reliable information about "student learning outcomes", which is the main indicator of the quality of education; making appropriate changes in subject curricula and textbooks after obtaining sufficient information about the student's knowledge and skills through assessment; acting as a means of combating some negative situations in education; serving the development of logical thinking

skills of new approaches to assessment, in contrast to memory-based assessment.

2. The problems and shortcomings revealed during the analysis of the current assessment system can be grouped as follows:

3. violation of assessment principles due to the lack of clearly defined assessment standards;

4. failure to describe the qualities of assessment methods and tools, failure to specify their main characteristics and criteria;

5. failure to pay attention to the technical qualities of assessment tools and use of non-standard tools;

6. failure to periodically carry out clarifications in the presence of different approaches to assessment and its methods;

7. lack of objective justification of the results of student activity in the process of assessing achievements;

8. limited experience in using modern assessment methods, low level of training of specialists in this field;

9. lack of interaction between specialists developing educational programs and those engaged in assessment activities;

10. lack of transparency of administrative procedures, lack of guarantees for the legality of assessment activities;

11. failure to analyze assessment results and prepare relevant reports.

The failure to solve these problems for a long time has resulted in the emergence of the following characteristic shortcomings in the assessment mechanism in the Azerbaijani education system:

- the existing assessment mechanism is not sufficiently focused on the needs of the learning process, does not become its integral part and does not serve to improve its quality;

- this mechanism is subjective in nature, as a rule, forces the student to memorize and encourages most students to study for the sake of getting a grade;

- only formal knowledge is assessed in the learning process, in most cases the goal is limited to writing a grade, and students are not given the opportunity to self-assess;

- during teaching, the teacher cannot create effective feedback with students through assessment;

- the limitations of existing assessment methods do not allow for the effective application of new learning technologies.

The education and assessment policy envisaged in Azerbaijan, while reflecting national interests, also necessitates the implementation of fundamental reform-oriented measures. The political, economic and social changes taking place in the world at the end of the 20th century directly require the implementation of the following specific goals:

- transition to more democratic methods of governance;

- establishment of an open civil society in the country;

- ensuring effective cooperation with developed countries;

- creation of international market relations and economic competition conditions;

- instilling a sense of national self-reliance.

Currently, large-scale reforms are being carried out in the education systems of many countries regarding the establishment of new assessment models, recording of students' educational achievements and the organization of final examinations at educational levels. Their main characteristics are characterized as follows:

- application and development of modern approaches in assessment and education policy, and in this regard, the rejection of outdated existing methods;

- selection of more progressive methods for conducting exams fairly and transparently;

- creation of relevant organizations within the education system for the implementation of new assessment mechanisms;

- considering the formation of a new assessment system as an integral part of educational reforms, a priority area and considering it in the context of the policy of developing modern curricula.

The development of the Assessment Concept serves to implement the following activities in order to realize these goals:

- justification of the need for progressive changes in curricula by reviewing assessment and examination systems, and the formation of modern views, cultural values, new rights and duties in society through proven mechanisms;

- In order to train national specialists in conditions of high competition and market relations, including new subjects and professions in the curriculum, focusing the main attention in the curricula on instilling practical skills and solving problems, mastering minimum standards by all students;

- In order to create an internal school assessment system that ensures the efficient functioning of the education system, developing high-quality assessment tools that meet modern content standards, implementing relevant procedures for final exams at educational

levels in a more fair and transparent manner, and creating a normative legal framework for regulating these issues;

- Creating a national assessment system that assists the government and other structures in managing the quality of education, increasing the efficiency of its organization, and expanding its sphere of influence, and ensuring the country's participation in international assessment and comparative studies.

Since reforms in the assessment system are an important tool for making positive changes in education, the process of creating a new assessment system in close connection with the reforms carried out in the field of curriculum and teacher training, and the formation of new approaches to the creation of textbooks and training materials are considered serious tasks. The work carried out in this direction aims to achieve the following:

- establishing a complete national system that links curriculum development and assessment activities in the country;

- using assessment to meet the needs of teaching and learning;

- establishing school-based and national assessment systems for effective management in order to obtain objective information about the quality of education, and ensuring the country's participation in international assessment studies.

To achieve these goals, the following strategic directions of action have been identified:

- developing a long-term strategy for assessing student achievement, school-based and national assessment concepts;

- creating school-based and national assessment, as well as a new examination system, ensuring the country's participation in international programs on assessing student achievement;

- preparing instructions, methodological tools, a management and logistical plan for the effective organization of student achievement assessment activities;

- developing appropriate assessment methods within the framework of curriculum reform training specialists in the creation of methods and tools, organizing teacher training in the use of these methods and tools;

- conducting an analysis of assessment results, preparing reports and establishing a system for assessing the quality of education in the country.

The main goal in determining content standards for subjects is to set goals for the students to master these standards. In order to achieve knowledge and skills in accordance with the adopted standards, students' activities should be continuously stimulated, and appropriate conditions should be created for them to master higher-level standards. In an optimal situation, no student should be allowed to lag behind throughout the academic year, on the contrary, the achievement of each student should be in the spotlight. In this regard, the assessment of student achievements is a continuous, dynamic and informal process. In this process, teachers' observation of students, students' performance of class work and homework, and their written and oral responses are important.

The results of a properly conducted assessment allow for decisions to be made about the teacher's activity, the extent to which this activity meets the needs of students, as well as the need to make appropriate changes to the curriculum, planning and textbooks.

Student achievement assessment is considered as a process of collecting information about a student's ability to acquire, use, and draw conclusions and serves the following purposes:

- monitoring student achievement (or regression);
- decision-making in the learning process;
- assessment of student learning outcomes;
- curriculum evaluation.

Assessment and learning processes are viewed as two interconnected aspects of education. Assessment, which is a systematic process, is structured as a means of effective feedback between learning outcomes and stakeholders by encompassing the following components:

assessment data. These include data reflecting students' achievements and attitudes to learning, teacher preparation level, characteristics of subject curricula, distribution of learning resources, and implementation mechanisms of activities;

data collection. This process is carried out by methods such as conducting tests, checking student assignments, conducting classroom interviews, observing the quality of subject curriculum implementation, student and teacher activities, analyzing grade tables and other school documents;

assessment results. These results are used to plan and direct the educational process, calculate grade points, make comparisons, issue educational documents and licenses, move from one level of education to another, formulate pedagogical theories, establish educational policy and monitor its effectiveness, allocate training resources, assess the quality of the curriculum and teaching, and also serve to inform the general public;

assessment standards. These standards determine the main criteria for assessing the quality of education, describe the quality of assessment methods and tools used for mutual assessment of student achievements and educational opportunities, and guarantee the legitimacy of the assessment process;

basic principles in assessing student achievements.

The following principles are observed in conducting all types of assessments:

relevance. The intended purpose and assessment are aligned. The assessment is planned in advance, the goals it will serve are determined, the essence, technical quality and main characteristics of the necessary information collected about the student are indicated, the methods of data collection and analysis are selected, the essence of the decision to be made is described. The results of the assessment reflect the established goals. Transparency of the relationships between the decisions made and the collected information is ensured.

Assessment procedures are internally consistent and form a unity;

Mutual assessment of achievements and educational opportunities. The following information on educational opportunities is collected through appropriate indicators: through intra-class indicators - the level of teacher professionalism, the content of training, the level of coordination of progress, assessments, the time allocated for training, the quality of resources and teaching aids that meet the student's requirements;

through indicators directly related to the education system - state standards, curricula, per capita education expenditures;

through other indicators - issues related to household problems;

ensuring the qualitative relevance and reliability of the collected information (validity and relevance). The quality of the data ensures the appropriateness of the decisions and activities made. The assessment objectives are realistically selected and measurable characteristics are assessed. The student's achievements are assessed according to the level of a specific task performed in a certain area within the opportunities created for him.

The assessment objectives and the intended relevant data allow for the same decision-making even when used at different times and are sufficiently stable;

transparency, fairness, mutual agreement and cooperation in assessment. The process of collecting data, the assessment criteria used by the teacher, and even his own level of professionalism are transparent, and the use of templates, assumptions, and other issues that distract students' attention is not allowed in assessment tasks. They are built in different contexts (without taking into account ethnic characteristics) according to the interests and capabilities of students. Assessment tasks are adapted accordingly for children with disabilities. The grade is given in a well-thought-out, purposeful, consistent with educational programs and other normative documents.

References

1. Ismayilova T. Summative assessment as an indicator of the quality of student achievement. // Scientific works, Institute of Educational Problems of the Republic of Azerbaijan, 2015, No. 3, pp. 176-178
2. Guliyeva L. Issues of assessing student achievement in modern education policy. // Scientific works, Institute of Educational Problems of the Republic of Azerbaijan, 2014, No. 2, pp. 87-88
3. Gurbanova X. Reliability indicator of assessment tools. // Scientific works, 2011, No. 2, pp. 151-153
4. Suleymanova A. Fundamentals of education. Baku, Education, 2014, 400 pp.
5. Talibov Y.R., Aghayev A.E., Eminov A., Isayev I. Pedagogy. Textbook. Baku, Adiloglu, 2003
6. Veysova Z., Mejidova A. Diagnostic assessment. // Curriculum, 2009, No. 4, pp. 13-45